

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: DAHIR

FIRST NAME: ISSA

PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: ONE

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List of 6 key concepts with page number in text:

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1–4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5–13)
3. Literature review (EUCLID 2019, 17–23)
4. Some Rules of Thumb for writing Papers (EUCLID 2019, 14–16)
5. What is a Guide and, Why should I need one (EUCLID 2019, 24–26)
6. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27–35)

ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD ONE

1)INTRODUCTION

My primary aim to study for my Ph.D. is to dedicate my time to research and keep writing. I felt that I worked in many contexts in my career, from Africa, the Middle East to Asia, and I wanted to write and help the upcoming generation shape their career well. The ACA 401D period one (1) coursepack already offers me this opportunity to get the basics right. The material is emphasizing writing details and commas, which we often ignore as a working populace.

The ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack video materials helped me set up and use Zotero. It is a beneficial research assistant tool to be used along the way. I am excited to use this tool in my research work and my day-to-day work going forward.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The course pack ACA-401D begins elaborating on essay writing, which, as a new student, I found intriguing!; "an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on an evidence" (EUCLID 2019, 1). it dissects how to start your essay, research the topic, organize your ideas, write the essay, reference the essay, and edit the essay. For a beginner, I found the material resourceful, educative, and kept me anticipating even more challenges. Our lecturer could tell us to write our response starting with an introduction, the body, and then end with conclusions in our undergraduate course, Reading through essay writing section of the coursepack, I now could not agree more on this structure's importance to communicate your ideas and answer the questions (EUCLID 2019, 3).

3) PLAGIARISM

As an avid user of social media and other communication forms, I found that people overlook the critical aspect of acknowledging the source of information and copying paste others' work and ideas without referencing. I am glad that the coursepack ACA 401D response paper one (1) put great emphasis on plagiarism. An example of plagiarism as outlined in the coursepack is "Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism" (EUCLID 2019, 5).

In this section, the coursepack gave the importance of citation, and Paraphrases was given great emphasis. "when you cite something in the text of your paper, you simply need only to put the author's name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from" (EUCLID 2019, 6). By doing this, you will acknowledge the source of information. In Paraphrases, most of us could get an idea in a discussion, online or from a book, and we tend to put in our words and claim to be of our concept. I will therefore be keen to detail and ensure that all these basics are taken care of in my future research work.

4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

Here the dos and don'ts in writing your thesis were detailed, and I found it interesting as we do not regularly pay attention. Some of the rules of thumb stipulated in the coursepack ACA 401D response paper one (1) are but are not limited to; "Do not make the writing boring and clumsy" and "Take the views you are discussing seriously" (EUCLID 2019, 15). which, to me, are essential elements to be considered when writing your thesis.

As young students, we rushed to complete our assignment without necessarily checking what we wrote word for word in our undergraduate study. Going through the initial coursework, I could easily sense that a comma should be a comma and no shortcut

to writing. I am pleased to be part of this beautiful journey as I continue to shape my writing skills yet further.

5) LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, proper use of commas, semicolon, punctuation, apostrophe, noun, verb, use of words such as its and it is, your and you are some of the critical elements emphasized. Eleven important reminders which are essential in writing highlighted too. However, the Grammarly tool provided by EUCLID for free is an indispensable tool in crosschecking our work while measuring the plagiarism percentage therein is laudable. I am excited to be using it in my day-to-day work.

6) WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE, AND WHY COULD I NEED ONE?

Different companies use different styles, but EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), which I also used when writing this response paper one (EUCLID 2019). I also agree that in academic writing, a writing guide is an indispensable tool as described below.

for any writer, but particularly for the freelance writer, a style guide should be an invaluable tool. Freelance writers should continually develop style guides for each customer or publication type that they work with. It is important that, as a freelancer, you can demonstrate an ability to follow a prescribed style, but equally that you can learn and record what your customers prefer from their comments. This will help increase your customers' satisfaction in the long term and will help place you as the supplier of choice for written material or assignments (EUCLID 2019, 25).

7) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I never paid attention to this until I read this, and I am glad that we are guided on which English to use so that we do not mix it all! I used to think British English is superior, but I learned that US English tends to be more popular because of the sheer number of the US population and influence.

8) CONCLUSION

Having gone through the initial student orientation file, the coursepack, videos, and sample papers, I felt already equipped with the technical know-how and courage of standing on my own throughout this course without necessarily having the guidance of a virtual instructor. Thanks to EUCLID and its dedicated team of professionals who made this possible. The only challenge I see moving forward is navigating through the course

while on a full-time job. The course calls for extra dedication and time to read and grasp the context of each study period that I envisage overcoming while giving myself that extra push.

I have gone through the materials provided. It was fun setting up Zotero and writing down my first response paper with mixed reactions of anxiety and pushing for perfection to have minimal mistakes and corrections from my instructors.

I think I have grasped the main concept of what is expected of me during the course. The use of the checklist for the student is an indispensable guide, so we do not veer off the road during our writing process, and of course, I need to stay alert although.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd edition. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.